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Extraction of natural blue colorant from *Genipa americana* L. using green technologies: Techno-economic evaluation

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1 **Abstract**

2 The use of green technologies for food production has increased in the last
3 years since they allow obtaining safe products for human consumption. This
4 study reports the optimization of the extraction of the natural blue colorant
5 genipin from genipap fruit using pressurized liquid extraction (PLE), low-
6 pressure extraction (LPSE), and pressing followed by LPSE (Press+LPSE).
7 The effects of the extracting solvent (water and ethanol), temperature (40,
8 50 and 60 °C) and pressure (0.1, 2, 5 and 8 MPa) on the extraction yield and
9 genipin recovery were investigated. An extensive economic evaluation of
10 the processes was also performed. The results showed that only the
11 extracting solvent influenced extraction yields and genipin recovery. Kinetic
12 curves demonstrated that it was possible to recover 90% of the genipin in a
13 very short time (less than 6 minutes) by Press+LPSE. Press+LPSE also
14 demonstrated a great economic feasibility with a payback time shorter than
15 1 year.

16 **Keywords:** Color additives; pressurized liquid extraction; solvent
17 extraction; pressing extraction; cost of manufacturing

18

19

20 **1. Introduction**

21 The food industry has been replacing synthetic additives with natural
22 ones due to the modern consumer's demand for healthier products. Among
23 the additives used in the food industry, colorants stand out because color is
24 one of the main attributes evaluated by consumers when deciding to
25 purchase a food product. Currently, synthetic colorants are recognized as
26 carcinogenic and allergenic products and are being widely rejected (Martins
27 *et al.*, 2016).

28 Brazil has a large diversity of plants that can be used to obtain
29 assorted colors, but there is a scarcity of natural colorants with blue color. In
30 this sense, unripe genipap (*Genipa americana* L), a native fruit from Brazil
31 rich in genipin appears as a natural source for obtaining the blue color.
32 Genipin is an iridoid that reacts spontaneously with primary amine groups
33 of amino acids, peptides or proteins in the presence of oxygen to form dark-
34 blue pigments (Ramos-de-la-Pena *et al.*, 2014, Náthia-Neves and Meireles
35 2018).

36 For many years, the use of genipin as a colorant was limited to only
37 few Asian countries, such as Japan and Korea, which allow the use of
38 genipin from *Gardenia jasminoides* Ellis fruits as food coloring (Lee *et al.*,
39 2003). The non-use of this natural colorant in foodstuffs is mainly due to
40 strict safety requirements in Europe and United States. However, this
41 scenario has changed since genipin colorant has been reported as a "fruit
42 juice" color additive in the United States (Title 21 CFR, Code of Federal
43 Regulations, § 73.250) (FDA 2009) and, more recently, the use of genipin
44 colorant for food was approved in Colombia (Brauch *et al.*, 2016).

45 Despite of the increased interest for these products, studies
46 investigating the extraction of blue colorant from genipap and its economic
47 viability are still scarce in literature. Nowadays, to be competitive in the
48 current market, processes to obtain pigment-rich products must be not only
49 efficient but also relatively cheap to enable its economic feasibility
50 (Alcázar-Alay, Osorio-Tobón, Forster-Carneiro, & Meireles, 2017). Factors
51 such as performance (obtaining as much product as possible), productivity
52 (requiring the least amount of processing time) and selectively (obtaining a
53 product rich in the substance of interest) should be considered when
54 determining the economic viability of a process (Prado, Prado, & Meireles,
55 2011).

56 Therefore, the purpose of this work was to obtain a genipin-rich
57 extract with blue color using the peeled genipap fruit as raw material and to
58 optimize the extraction with moderate / low pressures in order to provide a
59 technically and economically feasible process. In this sense, the economic
60 feasibility of the process was determined through the estimation of the cost
61 of manufacturing (COM), revenue, payback time and productivity
62 parameters. To the best of our knowledge, it is the first time that the genipin
63 production is economically evaluated to state its commercial feasibility.

64 **2. Materials and methods**

65

66 2.1 Raw material preparation

67 Unripe genipap fruits were acquired from Sítio do Bello (Paraibuna,
68 Brazil) in November 2016. The fruits were separated from peel with a knife
69 and crushed into small particles in a mixer (Philips Walita 400 W,

70 RI1364/07, Varginha, Brazil). After these processes, the raw material was
71 characterized according to moisture (method 920.151 from AOAC (1997));
72 ash (method 923.03 from AOAC (1997)); protein (method 970.22 from
73 AOAC (1997)); lipids (method from Bligh and Dyer (1959)) and
74 carbohydrates (calculated by difference). The density of the fruit was
75 measured using a glass pycnometer.

76 2.2 Extraction processes

77 Fig. 1 shows the paths followed in this study to optimize the genipin
78 extraction from peeled genipap fruit.

79 2.2.1 Pressurized liquid extraction (PLE)

80 All extraction assays were performed in a homemade unit described
81 and validated by Johner and Meireles (2016) (Fig. 2a). The parameters
82 evaluated for PLE were the solvent (water and ethanol), temperature (40, 50
83 and 60 °C) and pressure (0.1, 2, 5 and 8 MPa).

84 For each assay, 10 g (wet basis, w.b.) of raw material were placed in
85 a 100-mL stainless-steel extraction vessel with a metal filter on the bottom.
86 The void volume was filled with glass beads. The extraction vessel was
87 heated in a heating bath (Thermo Haake, DC30/DL30, Eindhoven,
88 Netherlands). Next, the extraction vessel was filled with a solvent using an
89 HPLC pump (Thermoseparation Products, California, USA) until the
90 desired pressure was reached, and the pressure was maintained for 5 min for
91 the static period. The solvent feed rate was 2 mL/min. After the static time,
92 the blocking valve (Autoclave Engineers, 10 V2071, Pennsylvania, USA)
93 and micrometric valve (Autoclave Engineers, 10 VRM2812, Pennsylvania,
94 USA) were opened and carefully adjusted to maintain the system pressure.

95 The solvent-to-feed mass ratio (S/F) was 5 (w.b.). Global yield (X_0) was
96 calculated as the ratio of the total extract obtained from the extraction and
97 the amount of raw material used on a dry basis.

98 2.2.2 Extraction kinetics study

99 2.2.2.1 Low-pressure solvent extraction (LPSE) kinetic

100 The kinetic experiments used to construct the overall extraction
101 curve (OEC) were performed under the optimal extraction conditions to
102 maximize the extraction yield and genipin recovery. As discussed in the
103 results section, the best results were obtained using water as the solvent at
104 40 °C and 0.1 MPa, i.e., ambient pressure, and thus, the codes for the
105 process will be substituted using the conventional acronym for low-pressure
106 solvent extraction, LPSE. The solvent feed rate was 8 mL/min, and the mass
107 of the raw material used was 40 g (w.b.). The extraction process was
108 performed as described in Section 2.2.1. An extraction time of 127 min was
109 adopted to ensure that the diffusion-controlled period was reached. The
110 kinetic experiments were replicated 2 times.

111 2.2.2.2 Press+LPSE (Pressing followed by LPSE) kinetic

112 At this stage, a mechanical press was used to obtain a concentrated
113 genipin extract without the use of a solvent. The diameter of the press was
114 19.8 mm. The pressure exerted by the piston on the plant matrix was 67
115 MPa and was controlled by a torque wrench (SATA, ST96304SC, Sorocaba,
116 Brazil). The press (Fig. 2b) was connected to the system, and the pressing
117 lasted approximately one and a half minutes. After pressing, the extraction
118 was performed as described in Section 2.2.2.1. The kinetic experiments
119 were replicated 2 times.

120 2.2.2.3 OEC modeling

121 The experimental data obtained from the OECs were fitted to a
122 three-lines spline model using the PROREG procedure with SAS 9.2 ®
123 software followed by the NLIN procedure according to Meireles (2008).
124 The fitted lines were attributed to three different steps based on classic
125 descriptions of the periods: the constant extraction rate (CER, Equation 1),
126 falling extraction rate (FER, Equation 2) and diffusion-controlled (DC,
127 Equation 3).

$$\text{for } t \leq t_1: m_{Ext}(t) = b_0 + a_1 t \quad (1)$$

$$t_{CER} \leq t \leq t_{FER}: m_{Ext}(t) = (b_0 - t_1 a_2) + (a_1 + a_2) t \quad (2)$$

$$\text{for } t \geq t_{FER}: m_{Ext}(t) = (b_0 - t_1 a_2 - t_2 a_3) + (a_1 + a_2 + a_3) t \quad (3)$$

128 where m_{Ext} is the extracted mass; t is the extraction time; b_0 is the linear
129 coefficient of the CER line; a_1 , a_2 and a_3 are the slopes of the CER, FER and
130 DC lines, respectively; t_{CER} is the CER time span; and t_{FER} is the end of the
131 FER period.

132 2.3 Extract analyses

133 2.3.1 Genipin quantification

134 Genipin content in the extracts was quantified by an HPLC-DAD
135 (Waters, Alliance E2695, Milford, USA) according to Náthia-Neves,
136 Nogueira, Vardanega and Meireles (2018). The genipin was separated in a
137 fused-core C18 column (Kinetex, 100×4.6 mm i.d.; $2.6 \mu\text{m}$; Phenomenex,
138 Torrance, USA) using a mobile phase of water (A) and acetonitrile (B) that
139 were both acidified with 0.1% formic acid and the following gradient: 0
140 min, 99% A; 9 min, 75% A; 10 min, 99% A and 13 min, 99% A. The

141 temperature and flow rate were 35 °C and 1.5 mL/min, respectively. Fig. 3
142 shows the chromatograms of the standards and the extracts obtained from
143 *Genipa americana* L.

144 2.3.2 Color analysis

145 Color was measured in a Hunterlab colorimeter (Hunter Associates
146 Laboratory, Inc., Reston, Virginia, USA) equipped with a D65 light source
147 with an angle of observation of 2° for all the samples. The extract color was
148 analyzed at room temperature, and the sampling was performed in triplicate.

149 2.4 Statistical analysis

150 The analysis of the influence of the parameters on the X_0 and genipin
151 recovery of the extracts was performed by analysis of variance (ANOVA)
152 using Minitab 16® software (Minitab Inc., State College, Pennsylvania,
153 USA) with a 95% confidence (p-value ≤ 0.05).

154 2.5 Economic evaluation

155 The models of the LPSE and Press+LPSE processes were built using
156 the commercial simulator SuperPro Designer® version 8.5 (Intelligen Inc.,
157 Scotch Plains, USA). The input parameters and process conditions were
158 determined according to the kinetic assays. The experimental data used to
159 simulate the LPSE and Press+LPSE are presented in Table 1. The dollar
160 quotation to estimate the costs of the local items was R\$ 3.17.

161 Cost estimation for the equipment on different scales were
162 performed using the power law (Equation 4) (Smith, 2005), where: C_1 is the
163 equipment cost with capacity Q_1 ; C_2 is the known base cost for equipment
164 with capacity Q_2 ; and n is a constant depending on equipment type (Green

165 and Perry, 2007, Smith, 2005, Turton et al., 2012). The base costs of the
166 equipment used in this work were based on an operating plant with two
167 extractors of 1 L (Table 2).

$$C_1 = C_2 \left(\frac{Q_2}{Q_1} \right)^n \quad (4)$$

168 Equipment costs in the scales studied were calculated by Equation 4
169 using the base cost data presented in Table 2. Thus, the total costs of the
170 LPSE plants at 10-L, 50-L and 100-L scales were US\$ 121,401.06, US\$
171 337,767.58 and US\$ 529,424.31, respectively. The total cost of the
172 LPSE+Press plants at 10-L, 50-L and 100-L scales were US\$ 130,270.55,
173 US\$ 360,691.61 and US\$ 563,930.63, respectively. The annual depreciation
174 rate considered was 10%, and the annual maintenance rate was US\$ 6.00/h.
175 The number of workers needed for the 10-L and 50-L plants was two and
176 for the 100-L plant three. The hourly cost of each worker was US\$ 13.80
177 (SuperPro cost database). The cost of utilities was taken from the SuperPro
178 database, and the chilled water cost was US\$ 0.40 /ton, the steam cost was
179 US\$ 12.00/ton, and the electricity cost was US\$ 0.10/kW.h. The water cost
180 was US\$ 0.05/ton.

181 The cost of manufacturing (COM) was calculated as the ratio
182 between the annual cost of operation and the annual production using the
183 cost tool in the simulator SuperPro Designer® (Intelligen Inc., Scotch
184 Plains, USA). The profitability indices evaluated were return on investment
185 (ROI), payback time, gross margin (GM), net present value (NPV) and
186 internal rate of return (IRR) after taxes, as described by Vardanega *et al.*
187 (2017a).

188

189 2.5.1 Sensitivity analysis

190 The sensitivity analyses were accomplished to explore the
191 uncertainties related to the prices and costs assumed to evaluate the process.
192 Thus, two acquisition costs for genipap were evaluated: US\$ 1.42/kg (usual
193 price of genipap in the region where the fruit is largely produced) and US\$
194 7.89/kg (price of genipap in regions far from the production region). As
195 extracts obtained from genipap are not yet commercialized, it is difficult to
196 establish a selling price for this product. Thus, a sensitivity study was
197 performed with five selling prices: *i*) US\$ 50.00/kg; *ii*) US\$ 100.00/kg; *iii*)
198 US\$ 150.00/kg; *iv*) US\$ 200.00/kg and *v*) US\$ 250.00/kg. The range of
199 selling prices evaluated was selected based on extracts obtained from
200 *Gardenia jasminoides* that are commercialized in Asian countries.

201

202 3. Results and discussion

203

204 3.1 Unripe genipap characterization

205 Table 3 presents the proximate composition of unripe genipap fruit.
206 These results are in agreement with that found by Náthia Neves *et al.*
207 (2017). The authors observed that the genipap fruit with peel presented 80%
208 moisture, 5% ash, 7% protein, 3% lipids and 84.7% carbohydrates. Data for
209 the whole fruit without peel were not found in the literature. The mesocarp
210 of the unripe genipap analyzed by Bentes *et al.* (2015) presented 80.9%
211 moisture, 4.97% ash, 3.24% proteins, 1.52% lipids, 41.19% total fiber and
212 49% carbohydrates on a dry basis. The same authors found that the
213 endocarp + seeds from unripe genipap fruits presented 68% moisture, 2.75%

214 ash, 9.97% proteins, 1.69% lipids, 46.05% total fiber and 39.54%
215 carbohydrates on a dry basis.

216 3.2 Effect of the process parameters on X_0 and genipin recovery

217 The analysis of variance (ANOVA, $\alpha = 0.05$) showed that only the
218 solvent significantly affected the X_0 (p-value = 0.024) and genipin recovery
219 (p-value = 0.001). Fig. 4 shows the isotherms obtained under the different
220 extraction conditions. The X_0 ranged from 30 to 45% (d.b.). A larger X_0 was
221 observed using water as a solvent, which may be related to the high content
222 of carbohydrates (84%), that are easily extracted with water (Vardanega *et*
223 *al.*, 2017b). In a previous study, it was observed that temperature had a
224 significant effect on X_0 and genipin recovery when 50 and 80 °C were
225 studied; the increase of temperature resulted in a decrease of genipin
226 recovery (Náthia-Neves *et al.*, 2017). However, the results obtained in this
227 study indicated that variations up to 10 °C in the process temperature had no
228 influence on the X_0 and genipin recovery. Therefore, 40 °C was selected
229 since it requires less energy consumption.

230 The non-influence of the pressure on the extraction using liquid
231 solvents has already been reported by some authors (Vardanega *et al.*,
232 2017c, Viganó *et al.*, 2016). This occurs because liquids are not
233 compressible fluids. According to Osorio-Tobón and Meireles (2013), even
234 under large pressure changes, the solvation power of the solvent is not
235 significantly affected. However, the use of a higher pressure can favor the
236 extraction of compounds located inside the matrix pores because the
237 pressure forces the solvent to penetrate places that are normally not reached
238 by the solvent at atmospheric pressure (Osorio-Tobón and Meireles 2013).

239 As no significant effect of pressure was observed for the genipin recovery it
240 suggests that genipin is located in cells that are easily accessible by the
241 solvent at lower pressures. From the point of industrial application,
242 processes involving low pressure are very interesting because the equipment
243 are of simple operation, has low cost and the product can be obtained in a
244 food grade (Silva et al., 2017).

245 The genipin recovery ranged from 51 to 92 mg/g RM (raw material).
246 The highest genipin recovery (92 mg/g RM) was obtained at 40 °C and 0.1
247 MPa using water as solvent, what is in agreement with the expected, since
248 genipin is an iridoid of polar characteristic (Balamurugan *et al.*, 2014, Wu
249 and Horn 2015). In the previous study, Náthia-Neves *et al.*, (2017) obtained
250 an extraction yield of 36% (d.b.) and a genipin recovery of 47 mg/g RM at
251 50 °C and 2 MPa using ethanol as solvent and unripe genipap (whole fruit
252 with peel) as raw material. Although this result was similar to those
253 observed in the present study, the color of the extracts was yellow-like.

254 Ramos-de-la-Peña *et al.*, (2015) extracted genipin from genipap fruit
255 using the HPP method at 130 MPa with water as solvent and obtained a
256 genipin recovery of 34 ± 2 mg/ g RM (w.b.) after 15 min of processing. The
257 recovery reported by these authors was 3 times lower than that obtained in
258 the present study, which can be attributed to the different parts of the
259 genipap used as raw material in each study: these authors used the genipap
260 fruit without seeds while the peeled fruit was used in the present study.
261 Furthermore, the principle of the extraction processes was also different,
262 since the HPP is based on the hydrostatic pressure while the extraction

263 condition that resulted the highest genipin recovery in this study is based on
264 the dynamic contact between the solvent and the raw material.

265 The highest genipin recovery (196 mg/ g RM, d.b) reported in the
266 literature was obtained by Bellé *et al.* (2018) by an enzyme-assisted
267 extraction in liquid-liquid aqueous system. The best condition was using the
268 Celluclast 10% enzyme at 36 °C and pH of 3.7. Although the genipin
269 recovery was 2.1 times superior than the obtained in this study, the
270 processing time was 4 times longer. These authors also studied the chitosan
271 gels crosslinked with genipin 0.5% and observed better textural and similar
272 rheological properties when compared to the chitosan crosslinked with
273 glutaraldehyde 3%, which makes the genipin an alternative to the use of
274 glutaraldehyde in chitosan crosslinking applications.

275

276 3.3 Color

277 Genipin is known to be a natural blue colorant, this colorant is the
278 cross-linked form of genipin (with proteins or amino acids). In this sense the
279 color analyses was performed in order to confirm if the extracts obtained
280 from genipap fruit presented the blue color in all evaluated conditions. The
281 color parameters of the extracts are presented in Table 4. All extracts
282 showed coloration in the blue region (b^* negative). The ethanolic extracts
283 showed lighter coloration than the aqueous extracts. The increase in
284 temperature favored a darker coloration in both solvents, and the aqueous
285 extract at 60 °C presented a color close to black (low L^*). These results
286 confirmed that the extracts obtained from unripe genipap fruits can be used

287 as a colorant by the food industry and supply a natural blue color currently
288 lacking in the food industry.

289 At this stage of the study, it was possible to select the extraction
290 condition that resulted the extract with the highest genipin recovery and blue
291 color to proceed the kinetic study in order to evaluate the kinetic behavior of
292 the extraction. The extraction parameters selected were: 40 °C and 0.1 MPa,
293 i.e., ambient pressure, using water as solvent.

294 3.4 Extraction kinetics

295 Overall extraction curves (OECs) based on the extraction yield and
296 genipin recovery are presented in Fig. 5. As an alternative for increasing the
297 genipin recovery with the minimal consumption of solvent, a mechanical
298 pressing step was added before the solvent extraction to obtain a
299 concentrated aqueous extract fraction. After pressing, the solvent extraction
300 was carried out to recover the remain genipin in the raw material. Thus, next
301 it will be presented the comparison of the OECs obtained without and with
302 the pressing step, named LPSE and Press+LPSE, respectively. As discussed
303 previously, the extraction performed with LPSE (40 °C and 0.1MPa) using
304 an S/F of 5 and an extraction time of approximately 25 minutes allowed an
305 extract yield of $40 \pm 2\%$ and a genipin recovery of 92.2 ± 0.4 mg/ g RM.
306 The extraction using only pressing (first point of Figures 5a and 5b) allowed
307 an extract yield of $26 \pm 2\%$ and a genipin recovery of 52 ± 10 mg/ g RM in
308 a time of 1.19 minutes.

309 The higher extraction yield obtained in the LPSE process (Fig. 5a)
310 can be explained by the fact that other compounds have been extracted from

311 the vegetable matrix (probably carbohydrates) over time, while the pressing
312 compaction caused in the Press+LPSE may have hampered the extraction of
313 other compounds from the plant matrix. Regarding the genipin recovery, at
314 the end of the OECs the genipin amount was the same for both processes
315 (LPSE and Press+LPSE), which shows that both processes were able to
316 deplete all genipin present in the raw material (Fig. 5b).

317 The OECs obtained for the LPSE and Press+LPSE processes
318 presented similar behaviors with three characteristic stages: CER, FER and
319 DC periods. Higher amounts of extract and genipin were obtained in the
320 CER and FER periods. However, it is possible to observe in Fig 5a that the
321 Press+LPSE reached the CER period faster than LPSE because pressing
322 may favored the mass transfer rate in this period. For the recovery of
323 genipin, although the CER and FER times of LPSE and Press+LPSE
324 processes were close, the genipin recovery in the CER period of the
325 Press+LPSE was higher than that of the LPSE (Fig. 5b). In addition, the
326 curves obtained by the Press+LPSE presented a DC (diffusion controlled)
327 period more pronounced than the curves obtained from the LPSE. This
328 indicates that the use of the press greatly contributed to the removal of
329 compounds from the vegetable matrix.

330 From the fitted data, it was possible to estimate the parameters of the
331 LPSE and Press+LPSE processes, as shown in Table 5. The t_{CER} for LPSE
332 (8.1 ± 0.9 min) was higher than the t_{CER} for Press+LPSE (5.89 ± 0.03 min).
333 The extraction yields obtained at these times for these processes were $30 \pm$
334 3% and $36 \pm 3\%$, respectively. These yields correspond to 64% of the total
335 yield of the LPSE (after 127 min) and 91% of the total yield of the

336 Press+LPSE (after 128 min). These results are consistent with those
337 reported in the literature, where approximately 50-90% of the total extract
338 amount was obtained in the CER period (Pereira and Meireles 2009). This
339 occurs because in the CER period the solute is easily accessible and
340 solubilized in the solvent (Soares *et al.*, 2016). Although the t_{FER} values for
341 the LPSE and Press+LPSE processes were similar, the yield obtained at this
342 time in the LPSE ($43 \pm 4\%$) was higher than the yield at that time in the
343 Press+LPSE ($38 \pm 3\%$). These yields correspond to 90% of the total yield of
344 LPSE (after 127 min) and 98% of the total yield of the Press+LPSE (after
345 128 min).

346 For genipin recovery using LPSE, t_{CER} resulted in a recovery of only
347 55% of the total genipin and t_{FER} resulted in 93% of the total genipin, while
348 for the Press+LPSE, 90% of the total genipin was recovered in the t_{CER} .
349 Therefore, the LPSE process should be performed for 22.2 min (t_{FER}), while
350 the Press+LPSE process should be performed for 5.84 min (t_{CER}).

351 3.5 Economic evaluation

352 Although the Press+LPSE demonstrated that the processing time
353 could be reduced from 22.2 min to approximately 5.84 min, it required the
354 addition of an additional unit operation to the process, which in turn
355 represent an additional cost to the equipment acquisition. To evaluate these
356 impact on the economic feasibility of the genipin production, a detailed
357 economic evaluation was performed.

358 3.5.1 Influence of scale-up on the COM and productivity

359 The LPSE and Press+LPSE processes were simulated to determine
360 the COM of the extract from unripe genipap fruit and the productivity and
361 total capital investment for different extraction vessel volumes (2×10 L, 2
362 $\times 50$ L and 2×100 L) and raw material costs (US\$ 1.42/kg and US\$
363 7.89/kg), and the results are shown in Fig. 6. Two raw materials costs were
364 considered for this simulation to evaluate the impact this variable on
365 economic viability of the processes because the acquisition cost vary
366 drastically depending on the genipap production region in Brazil.

367 Considering the raw material cost of US\$ 1.42/kg (Fig. 6a), the
368 COM ranged from US\$ 49.36/kg to US\$ 95.03/kg in the LPSE process and
369 from US\$ 46.28/kg to US\$ 80.34/kg in the Press+LPSE process. When the
370 raw material cost of US\$ 7.89/kg (Fig. 6b) was considered, the cost inherent
371 to raw material acquisition exerted a strong influence on the manufacturing
372 costs. The estimated COM ranged from US\$ 129.63/kg to US\$ 175.30/kg
373 for the LPSE and US\$ 140.08/kg to US\$ 174.15/kg for the Press+LPSE.

374 As observed in Fig. 6, the COM decreases with the increase in the
375 production scale. The same behavior was reported for the extraction of
376 carotenoids from pressed palm fibers using LPSE (Cardenas-Toro *et al.*,
377 2015), for the extraction of curcuminoids from deflavored turmeric using
378 PLE (Osorio-Tobón *et al.*, 2014) and for the extraction of phenolic
379 compounds from jabuticaba skins using PLE (Santos *et al.*, 2012). The
380 extract productivity obtained in the Press+LPSE process was 1.3 times
381 higher than that in the LPSE process. The higher productivity of the
382 Press+LPSE process is related to its shorter process time, which allows

383 more batches per year than the PLE process. The total cost of investment
384 showed little variation between the two processes.

385 The COM was calculated considering the costs of the raw material,
386 facilities, labor and utilities (Carvalho *et al.*, 2015). The percent contribution
387 of the economic parameters to the COM for the two raw material costs in
388 the five plant capacities studied are presented in Fig. 7. For the cost of raw
389 material of US\$ 1.42/kg, the facility components represent the largest
390 contribution to the COM in both LPSE and Press+LPSE processes. As the
391 scale increased, the contribution of labor and facility components to the
392 COM was reduced, which indicated the feasibility of the processes on larger
393 scales. In contrast, the contribution of raw materials increased as the scale
394 increased.

395 Raw materials are generally the components with the highest
396 contribution to the COM (Osorio-Tobón *et al.*, 2016). This can be easily
397 observed by increasing the cost of raw material to US\$ 7.89/kg (Fig. 7). In
398 this situation, the raw material becomes the component with the greatest
399 contribution to the COM for both LPSE and Press+LPSE processes. The
400 influence of the cost of raw material in the Press+LPSE is greater than that
401 in the LPSE because this process occurs more rapidly, and therefore, it
402 requires a greater amount of raw material to be processed. The change in the
403 raw material cost from US\$ 1.42/kg to US\$ 7.89/kg represents increases of
404 46% (10 L), 58% (50 L) and 62% (100 L) for the total COM for the LPSE
405 process and increases of 54% (10 L), 64% (50 L) and 67% (100 L) for the
406 total COM for the Press+LPSE process.

407 3.5.2 Sensitivity analysis

408 As genipin is not yet commercialized as a colorant worldwide, it is
409 difficult to predict its selling price. Thus, to evaluate the influence of the
410 extract selling price on the feasibility of the process, a sensitivity analysis
411 was performed using selling prices from US\$ 50.00 to 250.00/kg for the
412 extract. Table 6 and Table 7 present an executive summary of the project
413 indices, which were calculated for the LPSE and Press+LPSE processes at
414 the 100-L scale, respectively. The project indices for the 10 L and 50 L
415 scales are presented in the Supplementary Material.

416 The gross margin (GM) is an economic indicator used to estimate
417 the short-term benefits of a specific activity. This indicator is calculated as
418 the ratio between the annual profits and the annual revenues and is
419 expressed as a percentage (Vlysidis *et al.*, 2011). A higher GM indicates a
420 more attractive project. In Table 6 and 7, with a raw material cost of US\$
421 1.42/kg, the GM demonstrates positive values for the selling price of
422 extracts higher than US\$ 100.00 for the LPSE process and for all selling
423 prices for the Press+LPSE process. Using a raw material cost of US\$
424 7.89/kg, the GM presents positive values only for selling prices above US\$
425 150.00 for both the LPSE and Press+LPSE processes.

426 The return on investment (ROI) is the percentage of money
427 recovered annually from the plant's profit, and thus, a higher ROI indicates
428 a more desirable product (Vlysidis *et al.*, 2011). In general, a minimum ROI
429 of 5-10% is necessary to accept a project (El-Halwagi 2017, Fernández-
430 Ronco *et al.*, 2013). For a raw material cost of US\$ 1.42/kg, all evaluated

431 scenarios presented acceptable values of ROI, except for a selling price of
432 US\$ 50.00/kg for the extract using LPSE. However, for a raw material cost
433 of US\$ 7.89/kg, selling prices above US\$ 150.00/kg for the extract were
434 necessary to make the processes feasible.

435 Payback time represents the time required to recover the cost of
436 investment. Clearly, shorter payback times are more attractive; payback
437 times between 2 and 5 years are considered feasible. As expected, the best
438 payback occurs with higher selling prices and lower raw material costs for
439 both processes. The Press+LPSE process showed slightly lower payback
440 times than the LPSE process. However, for both processes, using a raw
441 material cost of US\$ 1.42/kg, selling prices above US\$ 100.00/kg for the
442 extract are required to make the processes feasible. However, for a raw
443 material cost of US\$ 7.89/kg, only selling prices above US\$ 150.00/kg for
444 the extract are feasible to reach acceptable payback times.

445 The net present value (NPV) represents the difference between the
446 present value of cash inflows and the present value of cash outflow. If the
447 NPV of a project is positive after assuming an interest rate of 7% (Osorio-
448 Tobón *et al.*, 2016), it can be considered feasible. Furthermore, to undertake
449 a project, the internal rate of return after taxes (IRR) should be as high as
450 possible because it represents the rate of return at which the project's NPV
451 is zero (Vucurovic *et al.*, 2012). Therefore, both processes became feasible
452 at selling prices higher than US\$ 100.00/kg for the extract with a raw
453 material cost of US\$ 1.42/kg; for the cost of raw material of US\$ 7.89/kg,
454 selling prices above US\$ 150.00/kg for the extract are needed.

455 It is worth to mention that the processes developed in this study
456 result products safe for food application and can be recognized as green
457 processes, since they use GRAS (Generally Recognized as Safe) solvents,
458 requires a low energy consumption and the biomass generated at the end of
459 the processes can be reused for the production of biofilms, animal feed or
460 even to produce bioenergy (Chemat et al., 2017). Furthermore, the processes
461 are economically viable because they enable obtaining a high yield of
462 genipin that is considered a compound of high added value for industry.

463 **4. Conclusion**

464 The results found in this work demonstrated that the peeled unripe
465 genipap is a suitable source of a blue color extract and that it was possible to
466 reduce the processing time from 22.2 min to 5.84 min by adding a pressing
467 step to the low-pressure solvent extraction method. From an economic
468 standpoint, both processes are applicable to industrial scales. The raw
469 material cost and selling price of the extract were demonstrated to greatly
470 affect the feasibility of the process. Thus, the present work showed the
471 commercial potential of genipap fruit and provide future perspectives for the
472 food industry since a natural blue colorant was obtained in a short time.

473

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480 **Author Contributions**

481 Grazielle Náthia-Neves: Collected the experimental data and drafted the
482 manuscript.

483 Renata Vardanega: Performed the economic analysis.

484 Maria Angela de Almeida Meireles: Designed the study and helped with the
485 results interpretation.

486

487 **References**

- 488 Alcázar-Alay, S. C., Osorio-Tobón, J. F., Forster-Carneiro, T., & Meireles, M. A. A.
489 (2017). Obtaining bixin from semi-defatted annatto seeds by a mechanical
490 method and solvent extraction: Process integration and economic
491 evaluation. *Food Research International*, **99**, 393-402.
- 492 AOAC (1997). Official methods of analysis of the Association of Official Analytical
493 Chemistry. AOAC International, Gaithersburg, USA (1997).
- 494 Balamurugan, M., Rajesh, S. & Manogaran, E. (2014). 'Genipin' – The Natural
495 Water Soluble Cross-linking Agent and Its Importance in the Modified
496 Drug Delivery Systems: An Overview. *Current Drug Delivery*, **11**, 139-145.
- 497 Bellé, A.S., Hackenhaar, C.R., Spolidoro, L.S., Rodrigues, E., Klein, M.P., Hertz, P.F.,
498 (2018). Efficient enzyme-assisted extraction of genipin from genipap
499 (*Genipa americana* L.) and its application as a crosslinker for chitosan gels.
500 *Food Chem* **246**, 266-274.
- 501 Bentes, Adria de S., Hugo A. L. de Souza, Jaime Amaya-Farfan, Alessandra. S Lopes,
502 and Lênio J. G. de Faria. 2015. "Influence of the composition of unripe
503 genipap (*Genipa americana* L.) fruit on the formation of blue pigment."
504 *Journal of Food Science and Technology* no. 52 (6):3919-3924.
- 505 Bligh, E. G. & Dyer, W. J. (1959). A rapid method of total lipid extraction and
506 purification. *Canadian journal of biochemistry and physiology*, **37**, 911-
507 917.
- 508 Brauch, J. E., Zapata-Porras, S. P., Buchweitz, M., Aschoff, J. K. & Carle, R. (2016).
509 Jagua blue derived from *Genipa americana* L. fruit: A natural alternative to
510 commonly used blue food colorants? *Food Research International*.
- 511 Cardenas-Toro, F. P., Alcázar-Alay, S. C., Coutinho, J. P., Godoy, H. T., Forster-
512 Carneiro, T. & Meireles, M. A. A. (2015). Pressurized liquid extraction and
513 low-pressure solvent extraction of carotenoids from pressed palm fiber:
514 Experimental and economical evaluation. *Food and Bioprocess
515 Processing*, **94**, 90-100.
- 516 Carvalho, P. I. N., Osorio-Tobón, J. F., Rostagno, M. A., Petenate, A. J. & Meireles,
517 M. A. A. (2015). Techno-economic evaluation of the extraction of turmeric
518 (*Curcuma longa* L.) oil and ar-turmerone using supercritical carbon
519 dioxide. *The Journal of Supercritical Fluids*, **105**, 44-54.
- 520 Chemat, F., Rombaut, N., Meullemiestre, A., Turk, M., Perino, S., Fabiano-Tixier,
521 A.-S., Abert-Vian, M., 2017. Review of Green Food Processing techniques.
522 Preservation, transformation, and extraction. *Innovative Food Science &
523 Emerging Technologies* **41**, 357-377.
- 524 El-Halwagi, M. M. (2017). Sustainable design through process integration:
525 fundamentals and applications to industrial pollution prevention,
526 resource conservation, and profitability enhancement. Butterworth-
527 Heinemann.
- 528 FDA (2009). - Food and Drugs Administration - Listing of color additives exempt
529 from certification; food, drug and cosmetic labeling: cochineal extract and
530 carmine declaration (21 CFR parts 73 and 101). *Federal register* **74** (2), . **74**
531 **(2)**, , 207-217.
- 532 Fernández-Ronco, M. P., de Lucas, A., Rodríguez, J. F., García, M. T. & Gracia, I.
533 (2013). New considerations in the economic evaluation of supercritical
534 processes: Separation of bioactive compounds from multicomponent
535 mixtures. *The Journal of Supercritical Fluids*, **79**, 345-355.
- 536 Green, D., & Perry, R. (2007). *Perry's Chemical Engineers' Handbook*, Eighth
537 Edition: McGraw-Hill Education.

- 538 Johner, J. C. F. & Meireles, M. A. d. A. (2016). Construction of a supercritical fluid
539 extraction (SFE) equipment: validation using annatto and fennel and
540 extract analysis by thin layer chromatography coupled to image. *Food
541 Science and Technology (Campinas)*, **36**, 210-247.
- 542 Lee, S.-W., Lim, J.-M., Bhoo, S.-H., Paik, Y.-S. & Hahn, T.-R. (2003). Colorimetric
543 determination of amino acids using genipin from *Gardenia jasminoides*.
544 *Analytica Chimica Acta*, **480**, 267-274.
- 545 Martins, N., Roriz, C. L., Morales, P., Barros, L. & Ferreira, I. C. F. R. (2016). Food
546 colorants: Challenges, opportunities and current desires of agro-industries
547 to ensure consumer expectations and regulatory practices. *Trends in Food
548 Science & Technology*, **52**, 1-15.
- 549 Meireles, M. A. A. (2008). Extraction of bioactive compounds from Latin American
550 plants. *Supercritical fluid extraction of nutraceuticals and bioactive
551 compounds*, 243-274.
- 552 Náthia-Neves, G. & Meireles, M. A. A. (2018). Genipap: A New Perspective on
553 Natural Colorants for the Food Industry. *Food and Public Health*, **8**, 21-33.
- 554 Náthia-Neves, G., Tarone, A. G., Tosi, M. M., Maróstica Júnior, M. R. & Meireles,
555 M. A. A. (2017). Extraction of bioactive compounds from genipap (*Genipa
556 americana* L.) by pressurized ethanol: Iridoids, phenolic content and
557 antioxidant activity. *Food Research International*, **102**, 595-604.
- 558 Náthia-Neves, G. N., Gislaine; Vardanega, Renata; Meireles, Maria Angela de
559 Almeida (2018). Identification and quantification of genipin and
560 geniposide from *Genipa americana* L. by HPLC-DAD using a fused-core
561 column. *Food Science and Technology (Campinas)*.
- 562 Osorio-Tobón, F. J., Carvalho, P. I. N., Rostagno, M. A., Petenate, A. J. & Meireles,
563 M. A. A. (2014). Extraction of curcuminoids from deflavored turmeric
564 (*Curcuma longa* L.) using pressurized liquids: Process integration and
565 economic evaluation. *The Journal of Supercritical Fluids*, **95**, 167-174.
- 566 Osorio-Tobón, J. F., Carvalho, P. I. N., Rostagno, M. A. & Meireles, M. A. A. (2016).
567 Process integration for turmeric products extraction using supercritical
568 fluids and pressurized liquids: Economic evaluation. *Food and Bioproducts
569 Processing*, **98**, 227-235.
- 570 Osorio-Tobón, J. F. & Meireles, M. A. A. (2013). Recent Applications of Pressurized
571 Fluid Extraction: Curcuminoids Extraction with Pressurized Liquids. *Food
572 and Public Health*, **3**, 289-303.
- 573 Panja, Palash. 2017. "Green extraction methods of food polyphenols from
574 vegetable materials." *Current Opinion in Food Science*.
- 575 Pereira, C. G. & Meireles, M. A. A. (2009). Supercritical Fluid Extraction of
576 Bioactive Compounds: Fundamentals, Applications and Economic
577 Perspectives. *Food and Bioprocess Technology*, **3**, 340-372.
- 578 Prado, Juliana M., Glaucia H. C. Prado, and M. Angela A. Meireles. 2011. "Scale-up
579 study of supercritical fluid extraction process for clove and sugarcane
580 residue." *The Journal of Supercritical Fluids* no. 56 (3):231-237.
- 581 Ramos-de-la-Peña, A. M., Montañez, J. C., Reyes-Vega, M. d. I. L., Hendrickx, M. E.
582 & Contreras-Esquivel, J. C. (2015). Recovery of genipin from genipap fruit
583 by high pressure processing. *LWT - Food Science and Technology*, **63**,
584 1347-1350.
- 585 Ramos-de-la-Peña, A. M., Renard, C. M., Wicker, L., Montanez, J. C., Garcia-Cerda,
586 L. A. & Contreras-Esquivel, J. C. (2014). Environmental friendly cold-
587 mechanical/sonic enzymatic assisted extraction of genipin from genipap
588 (*Genipa americana*). *Ultrason Sonochem*, **21**, 43-9.

589 Santos, D. T., Veggi, P. C. & Meireles, M. A. A. (2012). Optimization and economic
590 evaluation of pressurized liquid extraction of phenolic compounds from
591 jabuticaba skins. *Journal of Food Engineering*, **108**, 444-452.

592 Silla, H., (2003). *Chemical Process Engineering: Design and Economics*. Taylor &
593 Francis.

594 Silva, S., Costa, E.M., Calhau, C., Morais, R.M., Pintado, M.E., 2017. Anthocyanin
595 extraction from plant tissues: A review. *Critical reviews in food science*
596 *and nutrition* 57, 3072-3083.

597 Smith, R. (2005). *Chemical Process Design and Integration*. Chichester: Wiley.

598 Soares, J. F., Zabet, G. L., Tres, M. V., Lunelli, F. C., Rodrigues, V. M., Friedrich, M.
599 T., Pazinato, C. A., Bilibio, D., Mazutti, M. A., Carniel, N. & Priamo, W. L.
600 (2016). Supercritical CO₂ extraction of black poplar (*Populus nigra* L.)
601 extract: Experimental data and fitting of kinetic parameters. *The Journal*
602 *of Supercritical Fluids*, **117**, 270-278.

603 Turton, R., Bailie, R. C., & Whiting, W. B. (2009). *Analysis, synthesis, and design of*
604 *chemical processes*: Prentice Hall.

605 Vardanega, R., Carvalho, P. I. N., Albarelli, J. Q., Santos, D. T. & Meireles, M. A. A.
606 (2017a). Techno-economic evaluation of obtaining Brazilian ginseng
607 extracts in potential production scenarios. *Food and Bioproducts*
608 *Processing*, **101**, 45-55.

609 Vardanega, R., Carvalho, P. I. N., Santos, D. T. & Meireles, M. A. A. (2017b).
610 Obtaining prebiotic carbohydrates and beta-ecdysone from Brazilian
611 ginseng by subcritical water extraction. *Innovative Food Science &*
612 *Emerging Technologies*, **42**, 73-82.

613 Vardanega, R., Santos, D. T. & Meireles, M. A. A. (2017c). Proposal for
614 fractionating Brazilian ginseng extracts: Process intensification approach.
615 *Journal of Food Engineering*, **196**, 73-80.

616 Viganó, J., Brumer, I. Z., Braga, P. A. d. C., da Silva, J. K., Maróstica Júnior, M. R.,
617 Reyes Reyes, F. G. & Martínez, J. (2016). Pressurized liquids extraction as
618 an alternative process to readily obtain bioactive compounds from
619 passion fruit rinds. *Food and Bioproducts Processing*, **100**, 382-390.

620 Viganó, J., Zabet, G. L. & Martínez, J. (2017). Supercritical fluid and pressurized
621 liquid extractions of phytonutrients from passion fruit by-products:
622 Economic evaluation of sequential multi-stage and single-stage processes.
623 *The Journal of Supercritical Fluids*, **122**, 88-98.

624 Vlysidis, A., Binns, M., Webb, C. & Theodoropoulos, C. (2011). A techno-economic
625 analysis of biodiesel biorefineries: Assessment of integrated designs for
626 the co-production of fuels and chemicals. *Energy*, **36**, 4671-4683.

627 Vucurovic, D. G., Dodic, S. N., Popov, S. D., Dodic, J. M. & Grahovac, J. A. (2012).
628 Process model and economic analysis of ethanol production from sugar
629 beet raw juice as part of the cleaner production concept. *Bioresour*
630 *Technol*, **104**, 367-72.

631 Wu, S. & Horn, G. (2015). Genipin-rich material and its use. Google Patents.

Figure captions

Fig. 1. Flowchart of the optimization study of the genipin extraction.

Fig. 2. a) Experimental apparatus used for the extraction; b) the press.

Fig. 3. Representative HPLC/DAD chromatograms for genipin analysis: a) standard solution of genipin (625 $\mu\text{g} / \text{mL}$); b) aqueous extract from *Genipa americana* L. obtained at 40 °C and 0.1 MPa; c) ethanolic extract from *Genipa americana* L. obtained at 40 °C and 0.1 MPa. Retention time of genipin: 6.6 minutes.

Fig. 4. Isotherms obtained at different pressures: a) global yield (X_0); b) genipin recovery. Standard deviations of the X_0 and genipin recovery from ANOVA ($\alpha = 0.05$) were 4 and 11, respectively.

Fig. 5. Overall extraction curves obtained at 40 °C and 0.1 MPa using water as the solvent: a) extraction yield; b) genipin recovery. The error bars represent the amplitude which is the difference between the lowest and highest value divided by two.

Fig. 6. Influence of the system capacity on the COM, productivity and total capital investment of the LPSE and Press + LPSE processes: a) based on the cost of raw material of US\$ 1.42/kg; b) based on the cost of raw material of US\$ 7.89/kg.

Fig. 7. Composition of the COM for the LPSE and Press + LPSE processes with different raw material costs.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6

Figure 7

Table 1 - Experimental data for the process simulations

Equipment settings	LPSE	Press+LPSE	Unit
Extraction pressure	0.1	0.1	MPa
Extraction temperature	40	40	°C
S/F	4.0	1.5	kg solvent/ kg feed (w.b.)
Extraction time	25	7	min
Extraction yield	7.8	6.8	%
Extract genipin content	19.6	21.6	% (w.b.)
Final extract moisture after drying	3.3	1.7	%

Table 2 - Base equipment costs

Equipment	Unit base cost (US\$) ^a	n ^b	LPSE plant		Press+LPSE plant	
			Number of equipment/instruments	Total base cost (US\$) ^a	Number of equipment/instruments	Total base cost (US\$) ^a
Jacketed extraction vessel ^c	6,270.00	0.82	2	12,540.00	2	12,540.00
Heating bath	2,063.09	0.59	1	2,063.09	1	2,063.09
Electric liquid pump	3,920.00	0.55	1	3,920.00	1	3,920.00
Dryer	8,000.00	0.59	1	8,000.00	1	8,000.00
Press ^d	8,479.50	0.59	0	0.00	2	16,959.00
Micrometer valve	1,090.00	0.6	2	2,180.00	2	2,180.00
Block valve	220	0.6	4	880.00	4	880.00
Safety valve	310	0.6	2	620.00	2	620.00
Piping, connectors, crossheads, mixers and splitter	3,660.00	0.6	1	3,660.00	1	3,660.00
Structural material for supporting the equipment	4,060.00	0.6	1	4,060.00	1	4,060.00
Manometer	410	-	2	820.00	2	820.00
Temperature controller	310	0.6	2	620.00	2	620.00
Total				39,363.09		56,322.09

^a Based on an operating plant with two 1-L extractors from Osorio-Tobón et al. (2016) and Viganó et al. (2017).

^b *n* constant depending on the equipment type based on Green and Perry (2007), Silla (2003), Smith (1995) and Turton et al. (2009).

^c Supporting pressures up to 60 MPa.

^d Direct quotation.

Table 3 - Proximate composition (% w/w) of unripe genipap fruit

Parameter	Results
Moisture	81.02 ± 0.02%
Ash	5.1 ± 0.1%
Lipids	4.0 ± 0.4%
Protein	6.9 ± 0.2%
Carbohydrates	84%
True density	1006.5 ± 0.1 kg/m ³

Table 4 - Color parameters for the unripe genipap fruit extracts

Solvents	T (°C)	P (MPa)	L*	a*	b*	C*	H*
Ethanol	40	0.1	4.3 ± 0.1	-0.33 ± 0.04	-3.2 ± 0.1	3.2 ± 0.1	264.1 ± 0.8
		2	11.7 ± 0.2	-1.4 ± 0.1	-1.7 ± 0.1	2.2 ± 0.1	231 ± 2
		5	11.9 ± 0.6	-2.7 ± 0.4	-2.8 ± 0.2	3.9 ± 0.3	226 ± 5
		8	27.39 ± 0.01	-0.6 ± 0.1	-2.23 ± 0.02	2.3 ± 0.02	256 ± 1
	50	0.1	5.6 ± 0.1	-0.65 ± 0.01	-3.9 ± 0.1	4 ± 0.1	260.7 ± 0.3
		2	10.8 ± 0.1	-1.2 ± 0.1	-1.3 ± 0.1	1.83 ± 0.06	227 ± 4
		5	10.7 ± 0.2	-1.7 ± 0.1	-1.3 ± 0.2	2.1 ± 0.1	217 ± 5
		8	9.6 ± 0.1	-1.7 ± 0.1	-2 ± 0.2	2.7 ± 0.1	230 ± 4
	60	0.1	4.1 ± 0.2	-1.12 ± 0.01	-3.9 ± 0.1	4.0 ± 0.1	255 ± 3
		2	8.9 ± 0.8	-2.1 ± 0.2	-3.2 ± 0.2	3.8 ± 0.1	237 ± 4
		5	7.8 ± 0.9	-1.3 ± 0.1	-3.9 ± 0.3	4.2 ± 0.3	252 ± 2
		8	10 ± 0.3	-2 ± 0.1	-3.6 ± 0.2	4.2 ± 0.2	241 ± 2
Water	40	0.1	24.84 ± 0.01	-0.38 ± 0.02	-1.47 ± 0.02	1.51 ± 0.02	255.6 ± 0.8
		2	7.36 ± 0.04	-1 ± 0.1	-2.4 ± 0.1	2.6 ± 0.1	247 ± 2
		5	8.11 ± 0.03	-1 ± 0.1	-2.1 ± 0.2	2.3 ± 0.1	244 ± 4
		8	7.59 ± 0.03	-1.7 ± 0.1	-3 ± 0.1	3.4 ± 0.1	241 ± 2
	50	0.1	3.48 ± 0.04	-1.1 ± 0.1	-2.74 ± 0.05	2.9 ± 0.05	248.2 ± 0.9
		2	5.6 ± 0.02	-1.24 ± 0.06	-2.9 ± 0.1	3.194 ± 0.06	247 ± 1
		5	5.71 ± 0.02	-1.4 ± 0.1	-1.5 ± 0.1	2.04 ± 0.05	227 ± 3
		8	5.3 ± 0.03	-1.8 ± 0.1	-1.9 ± 0.1	2.71 ± 0.08	227 ± 2
	60	0.1	3.72 ± 0.04	-1.15 ± 0.05	-2.88 ± 0.05	3.10 ± 0.05	248 ± 1
		2	4.61 ± 0.03	-1.1 ± 0.1	-3.8 ± 0.1	4.01 ± 0.05	254 ± 1
		5	3.55 ± 0.04	-1.14 ± 0.05	-1.88 ± 0.05	2.35 ± 0.03	233 ± 2
		8	3.91 ± 0.02	-1.1 ± 0.1	-3.97 ± 0.04	4.12 ± 0.04	255 ± 1

L*: luminosity: black (L* = 0) and white (L* = 100); a*: green color (-) and red color (+); b*: blue color (-) and yellow color (+); C*: chroma; H*: hue angle.

Table 5 - Kinetic parameters estimated by the spline model for the extraction yield and genipin recovery.

Extraction yield (d.b.)		
Kinetic parameters	LPSE	Press+LPSE
t_{CER} (min)	8.1 ± 0.9	5.89 ± 0.03
R_{CER} (%)	30 ± 3	36 ± 3
$M_{CER} \times 10^6$ (kg/s)	4.23 ± 0.03	2.7 ± 0.2
$Y_{CER} \times 10^2$ (kg extract/kg water)	3.2 ± 0.3	2.0 ± 0.2
R^2	1	1
t_{FER} (min)	23.3 ± 0.2	21.8 ± 0.3
R_{FER} (%)	43 ± 4	38 ± 3
$M_{FER} \times 10^6$ (kg / s)	1.0 ± 0.1	0.3 ± 0.2
$Y_{FER} \times 10^3$ (kg extract/kg water)	7.5 ± 0.1	2.5 ± 0.2
R^2	0.978	1
Genipin recovery (d.b.)		
Kinetic parameters	LPSE	Press+LPSE
t_{CER} (min)	5.8 ± 0.6	5.84 ± 0.02
R_{CER} (%)	4.9 ± 0.6	7.7 ± 1.2
$M_{CER} \times 10^6$ (kg/s)	1.0 ± 0.1	0.7 ± 0.1
$Y_{CER} \times 10^3$ (kg genipin/kg water)	7.5 ± 0.1	5.0 ± 0.1
R^2	0.999	1
t_{FER} (min)	22.2 ± 0.2	21.7 ± 0.4
R_{FER} (%)	8.3 ± 0.6	8.4 ± 1.2
$M_{FER} \times 10^7$ (kg/s)	1.7 ± 0.1	0.5 ± 0.1
$Y_{FER} \times 10^3$ (kg genipin/kg water)	1.3 ± 0.1	0.4 ± 0.1
R^2	1	0.999

d.b. = dry basis; t_{CER} = duration of constant extraction rate period; R_{CER} = yield for CER period; M_{CER} = mass transfer rate for CER period; Y_{CER} = mass ratio of solute in fluid phase at extractor outlet for CER period; t_{FER} = duration of falling extraction rate period; R_{FER} = yield for FER period; M_{FER} = mass transfer rate for FER period; Y_{FER} = mass ratio of solute in fluid phase at extractor outlet for FER period.

Table 6 - Project indices of the LPSE process at a 100-L scale

Selling Price (US\$/kg)	GM (%)	ROI (%)	Payback time (year)	IRR (%)	NPV (US\$) (at 7% interest)
Raw material cost = 1.42 US\$ / kg					
50.00	-2.13	7.79	12.84	N/A	-422,000.00
100.00	48.94	28.83	3.47	22.42	1,121,000.00
150.00	65.96	49.57	2.02	38.05	2,647,000.00
200.00	74.47	70.32	1.42	51.17	4,173,000.00
250.00	79.57	91.07	1.10	62.27	5,682,000.00
Raw material cost = 7.89 US\$ / kg					
50.00	-168.24	-47.18	N/A	N/A	-4,576,000.00
100.00	-34.12	-14.32	N/A	N/A	-2,067,000.00
150.00	10.59	14.36	6.96	8.36	87,000.00
200.00	32.94	34.08	2.93	27.11	1,613,000.00
250.00	46.35	53.79	1.86	41.48	3,139,000.00

NA: Not applicable; ROI: Return on investment; IRR: Internal rate of return after taxes; NPV: Net present value.

Table 7 - Project indices of the Press+LPSE process at a 100-L scale

Selling Price (US\$/kg)	GM (%)	ROI (%)	Payback time (year)	IRR (%)	NPV (US\$) (at 7% interest)
Raw material cost = 1.42 US\$ / kg					
50.00	5.85	9.97	10.03	2.11	-272,000.00
100.00	52.92	35.34	2.83	27.89	1,713,000.00
150.00	68.62	60.72	1.65	45.39	3,706,000.00
200.00	76.46	86.09	1.16	59.77	5,685,000.00
250.00	81.17	111.46	0.90	72.11	7,651,000.00
Raw material cost = 7.89 US\$ / kg					
50.00	-185.01	-64.97	N/A	N/A	-6,453,000.00
100.00	-42.50	-25.58	N/A	N/A	-3,176,000.00
150.00	5.00	11.45	8.73	5.23	-115,000.00
200.00	28.75	35.09	2.85	28.20	1,856,000.00
250.00	43.00	58.72	1.70	45.08	3,849,000.00

NA: Not applicable; ROI: Return on investment; IRR: Internal rate of return after taxes; NPV: Net present value.

Supplementary data

Table S.1 - Project indices of the LPSE process

LPSE	Scenario	Selling Price (US\$/kg)	GM (%)	ROI (%)	Payback time (year)	IRR (%)	NPV (US\$) (at 7% interest)
Raw material value = 1.42 US\$/Kg							
2 x 100 L	1	50	-2.13	7.79	12.84	N/A	-422,000
	2	100	48.94	28.83	3.47	22.42	1,121,000
	3	150	65.96	49.57	2.02	38.05	2,647,000
	4	200	74.47	70.32	1.42	51.17	4,173,000
	5	250	79.57	91.07	1.1	62.27	5,682,000
2x 50 L	6	50	-20.62	2.94	34.07	N/A	-479,000
	7	100	39.69	21.5	4.65	15.7	368,000
	8	150	59.79	37.82	2.64	29.61	1,131,000
	9	200	69.85	54.14	1.85	41.02	1,894,000
	10	250	75.88	70.47	1.42	51.17	2,657,000
2x 10 L	11	50	-96.63	-6.12	N/A	N/A	-321,000
	12	100	1.69	8.88	11.27	N/A	-83,000
	13	150	34.46	17.99	5.56	11.8	70,000
	14	200	50.84	27.11	3.69	20.55	222,000
	15	250	60.67	36.23	2.76	28.05	375,000
Raw material value = 7.89 US\$/Kg							
2 x 100 L	16	50	-168.24	-47.18	N/A	N/A	-4,576,000
	17	100	-34.12	-14.32	N/A	N/A	-2,067,000
	18	150	10.59	14.36	6.96	8.36	87,000
	19	200	32.94	34.08	2.93	27.11	1,613,000
	20	250	46.35	53.79	1.86	41.48	3,139,000
2x 50 L	21	50	-186.73	-40.58	N/A	N/A	-2,566,000
	22	100	-43.36	-14.45	N/A	N/A	-1,312,000
	23	150	4.42	10.29	9.72	3.05	-143,000
	24	200	28.32	25.96	3.85	20.08	613,000
	25	250	42.65	41.64	2.4	32.73	1,376,000
2x 10 L	26	50	-262.74	-30.66	N/A	N/A	-740,000
	27	100	-81.37	-15.8	N/A	N/A	-490,000
	28	150	-20.91	-0.94	N/A	N/A	-239,000
	29	200	9.32	11.7	8.55	4.77	-30,000
	30	250	27.45	20.61	4.85	14.77	119,000

NA: Not applicable; ROI: Return on investment; IRR: Internal rate of return after taxes; NPV: Net present value.

Table S.2 - Project indices of the Press+LPSE process

Press + LPSE	Scenario	Selling Price (US\$/kg)	GM (%)	ROI (%)	Payback time (year)	IRR (%)	NPV (US\$) (at 7% interest)
Raw material value = 1.42 US\$/Kg							
2 x 100 L	31	50	5.85	9.97	10.03	2.11	-272,000
	32	100	52.92	35.34	2.83	27.89	1,713,000
	33	150	68.62	60.72	1.65	45.39	3,706,000
	34	200	76.46	86.09	1.16	59.77	5,685,000
	35	250	81.17	111.46	0.9	72.11	7,651,000
2x 50 L	36	50	-9.2	5.47	18.28	N/A	-395,000
	37	100	45.4	26.58	3.76	20.55	651,000
	38	150	63.6	46.47	2.15	35.86	1,647,000
	39	200	72.7	66.36	1.51	48.83	2,644,000
	40	250	78.16	86.25	1.16	59.77	3,632,000
2x 10 L	41	50	-63.47	-3.19	N/A	N/A	-289,000
	42	100	18.27	12.62	7.92	6.02	-14,000
	43	150	45.51	23.74	4.21	17.89	181,000
	44	200	59.13	34.85	2.87	27.27	380,000
	45	250	67.31	45.96	2.18	35.55	579,000
Raw material value = 7.89 US\$/Kg							
2 x 100 L	46	50	-185.01	-64.97	N/A	N/A	-6,453,000
	47	100	-42.5	-25.58	N/A	N/A	-3,176,000
	48	150	5	11.45	8.73	5.23	-115,000
	49	200	28.75	35.09	2.85	28.2	1,856,000
	50	250	43	58.72	1.7	45.08	3,849,000
2x 50 L	51	50	-200.05	-54.66	N/A	N/A	-3,523,000
	52	100	-50.03	-23.31	N/A	N/A	-1,884,000
	53	150	-0.02	8.04	12.44	N/A	-275,000
	54	200	24.99	26.85	3.72	21.02	722,000
	55	250	39.99	45.66	2.19	35.86	1,719,000
2x 10 L	56	50	-254.32	-37.34	N/A	N/A	-919,000
	57	100	-77.16	-19.39	N/A	N/A	-591,000
	58	150	-18.11	-1.45	N/A	N/A	-263,000
	59	200	11.42	13.22	7.57	7.11	3,000
	60	250	29.14	23.98	4.17	18.2	195,000

NA: Not applicable; ROI: Return on investment; IRR: Internal rate of return after taxes; NPV: Net present value.